

The future of magnetic resonance imaging: our experience and literature review of actual tendencies*

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Abstract

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a modern method of imaging diagnostics and is the method of choice in the diagnosis of many different diseases. The method is used in all medical specialties, especially in oncology, neurosurgery, orthopedics, neurology, pediatrics, urology, gastroenterology, cardiology, and cardiac surgery. MRI examinations are increasing more and more, but unfortunately, the method is not equally available everywhere, as it is expensive and complicated to perform and interpret. This requires a new approach in the development of new devices that are more compact and cheaper. In addition, great efforts are being made in the development of specialized software, and, above all, the introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) will improve the speed and accuracy of interpretation. The progress that we expect in the future will allow more accessible examinations, reduce costs, and increase the accuracy of diagnosis. All this, given the lack of ionizing radiation, makes MRI the imaging method of the future.

Keywords

Artificial intelligence, diagnostic innovation, imaging diagnostics, medical technology trends, MRI

Introduction

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a method that has been used in medicine for 50 years. MRI relies on a strong magnetic field and radio waves, which produce high-quality images of the human body. This is its great advantage

over the scanner (computed tomography), X-rays, and PET scanners—magnetic resonance does not use X-rays and is considered completely harmless. The only contraindications for performing an MRI are having a pacemaker and some metal implants. Another negative aspect of magnetic resonance scanning is that the examination

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is long (approximately half an hour), but thanks to the introduction of new tomographs and optimization of protocols, with the latest generation of devices, the time has been shortened and in certain cases reaches only 15 minutes. Nowadays, approximately 50,000 magnetic resonance scanners are used throughout the world, and their number has increased significantly in Bulgaria in recent years. MRI is a widely used method in hospital and outpatient care, and thanks to it, patients receive accurate diagnoses, staging, and follow-up. Compared to a CT scan, MRI provides a more detailed image of soft tissues and is an indispensable method in the study of certain diseases (Plewes et al. 2012).

The advantages of the method in neurological diseases are better imaging of the posterior cranial fossa, brainstem, and cerebellum than CT; excellent differentiation of white from gray brain matter allows for precise diagnosis of demyelinating processes, dementia, Alzheimer's disease, and epilepsy. Modern MRI, in addition to structural information, also provides functional information about the central nervous system, which allows for precise definition of the detected process (Frizzell et al. 2022).

MRI is also used in cardiovascular diseases, allowing for accurate functional and structural assessment of the heart, which is especially important in myocardial ischemia, cardiomyopathy, myocarditis, vascular diseases, and congenital heart diseases. The method allows imaging of blood vessels without the use of contrast material, which is especially valuable in patients with renal failure or allergic reactions who cannot be diagnosed with a contrast-enhanced scanner (Russo et al. 2020).

Magnetic resonance imaging is an indispensable method for imaging joints and soft tissues and has an advantage over the spine scanner, allowing more accurate diagnoses of a number of diseases such as disc herniations, protrusions, spondylolisthesis, spondylosis, osteochondrosis, Bechterew's disease, tumors, degenerative diseases, and inflammatory diseases, and also in the assessment of traumatic changes (Bruno et al. 2019).

In urology, MRI occupies a central place in the diagnosis of the prostate due to better tissue contrast and clear definition of lesions, which is much more detailed than ultrasound and CT scanning. When detecting suspicious findings for cancer, a biopsy is performed using a special ultrasound device that overlays the magnetic resonance image (fusion biopsy), thus minimizing the possibility of missing the finding (O'Shea and Harisinghani 2022).

MRI has also become necessary in recent years as a method for diagnosing the hepatobiliary system, allowing for accurate characterization of findings in the liver, pancreas, bile, and bile ducts. The advantages of the method are that it is possible to assess a given lesion using specific protocols such as diffusion, dynamic contrast enhancement, and, above all, noninvasive imaging of the bile ducts—magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography. In recent years, the examination of the intestines using MRI—magnetic resonance enterography and colonography—has also become necessary, allowing their examina-

tion in a noninvasive way without causing discomfort to the patient (Swensson et al. 2021).

The lack of radiation makes magnetic resonance the method of choice for pregnant women and young children. MRI can be performed in the second or third trimester of pregnancy, with the only contraindication being the use of contrast material. Special protocols have been developed for fetal assessment, making the method particularly useful in detecting central nervous system malformations and various placental changes.

Methods

The MRI machine used is Siemens MAGNETOM Vida 3 Tesla. The AI software used is Siemens Deep Resolve in MRI. A comparison between normal images obtained by the MRI machine and AI-enhanced images is made. The first 3T MRI in the Plovdiv region, one of the few in Eastern Europe for research only, is situated in the Translational Neuroscience Complex (Fig. 1). This is a research cluster infrastructure that works in close cooperation with similar structures at the national and international levels. Such equipment is unique in its purpose not only for Bulgaria but also in the whole of Southeast Europe—it is created exclusively for scientific research purposes.

Translational medicine aims to transfer (translate) fundamental scientific research to clinical practice. In turn, translational neuroscience seeks to integrate basic research on brain activity *in vivo* with the needs of patients suffering from diseases of the nervous system, which are the subject of neurology, psychiatry, and neurosurgery. The research complex was created on the basis of an innovative theory of translational validity. According to it, there is a correspondence between clinical tests and brain activity measured by functional magnetic resonance imaging.

A multidisciplinary team of university neurologists, neurosurgeons, psychiatrists, pediatricians, pathophysiologists, anatomists, and imaging diagnosticians is engaged.

Results

Limitations in signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and spatial resolution, motion artifacts, and longer scan times can sometimes be limiting factors in MRI, depending on the organ of interest. Artificial intelligence is entering various areas of imaging diagnostics. One of its fundamental applications is to reformat images to make them better and smooth out their imperfections.

Fig. 2 shows an image reconstructed by artificial intelligence, which significantly improves the image, allowing for more accurate diagnosis and demonstrating even the smallest change.

Fig. 3 shows a case of a reconstructed image of an ankle, which again shows the possibilities of overcoming the high noise in the image, which makes it more difficult to diagnose.

Figure 1. The Translational Neuroscience Complex is a structure at the Medical University – Plovdiv, the result of a successfully completed grant project under the Operational Program „Development of the Competitiveness of the Bulgarian Economy“ 2007–2013 under the management of the Ministry of Economy.

Figure 2. MRI of the foot—proton density and axial plane. The right image is the original image of the foot; the left image is AI-enhanced with better quality and less noise.

Figure 3. MRI of the ankle—proton density and sagittal plane. The right image is the original image of the ankle; the left image is AI-enhanced with better quality and less noise.

Discussion

MRI is a method created in the 1970s and is already over 50 years old. The method is one of the most powerful medical modalities ever invented and is already the gold standard for a number of diseases. In the developed world, magnetic resonance imaging studies are increasing in number, and in some regions they even surpass computed tomography studies in number (Lundervold et al. 2019).

The most significant application of MRI is in the field of soft tissues, but it is also an indispensable method for tumors, strokes, and degenerative changes. MRI is better at diagnosing diseases in the small pelvis, especially the prostate and uterus. The method detects the localization of malignant processes with high accuracy, and accurate staging and monitoring are performed. In recent years, several software solutions have been created, especially for oncological patients, and artificial intelligence assists radiologists in almost every aspect of diagnosis. Moreover, artificial intelligence „sees“ things that can be overwhelming to a person and can perform calculations that are beyond the power of specialists (Kirkham et al. 2006; Fernandes et al. 2022).

The horizon for progress of magnetic resonance tomographs is clear—the machines will be more compact, which will significantly reduce their price and reduce the require-

ments for the premises, which will also save hospitals' finances. The high cost of cooling the machine will also be minimized. After years of raising the magnetic field, which has already reached 7T, the trends are now for the opposite development—reduction of the magnetic field, which will lead to poorer-quality images (Barisano et al. 2019). However, this drawback can be overcome thanks to the rapid development of artificial intelligence. The poor-quality original images have been significantly improved thanks to special software, and in various demonstrations, computer-generated images are indistinguishable from those generated by magnets with a higher field.

In addition to the obvious benefits of improving image quality, artificial intelligence has the potential to make MRI more accessible. Today's machines are bulky, cumbersome, expensive, and require large premises (Lin et al. 2021; Pierre et al. 2023). All this leads to a high initial investment and high maintenance costs. The reduction in the volume of the machines, the reduction of the magnetic field, and, above all, the need to use less helium will significantly reduce hospital costs (de Rooij et al. 2022; Kasasawa 2022). Our experience with images reconstructed with artificial intelligence shows that even images of insufficient quality can be improved, which will lead to cheaper and, above all, faster examinations, which will reduce the

cost of the examination itself, making MRI a routine diagnostic method considering its great advantages.

Another big advantage is the facilitation of the work of radiology technicians (Kabasawa 2022). MRI scanning is a very complicated process that requires in-depth technical knowledge, as well as good knowledge of physics and medicine (Hussain et al. 2022). In conditions of labor shortage, qualified radiology technicians are hard to find and are overwhelmed with work. Artificial intelligence has the potential to automate examinations and facilitate the scanning process.

The future of MRI is invariably linked to artificial intelligence (Lee et al. 2019). The main advantage of the use of convolutional networks is the ability to perform faster research, thus improving patient comfort and cost-effectiveness. The reconstruction of images with the help of artificial intelligence is the next big step in the development of MRI. The neural network-based Deep Resolve technology is achieved quickly without compromising its quality. The main technologies are Deep Resolve Gain and Deep Resolve Sharp, which aim to obtain sharp, high-resolution images based on lower-quality images, including the processing of raw data (Glielmo et al. 2024).

Conclusion

The integration of AI in MRI is already transforming medical imaging. The potential for AI in MRI is vast, offering numerous benefits and promising to revolutionize diagnostics and treatment in healthcare.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

LC wrote the draft of the manuscript. MD, GK, and BH were involved in the conceptualization, providing images, and validating the text. TV reviewed and edited the manuscript. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript before submission.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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